

Base Dissociation Constants (pK_b) of Antitubercular Compounds containing 2-Carboxyphenyl Sulphide and 2-Carboxyphenyl Sulphone Moieties

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The amines and Schiff's bases containing 2-carboxyphenyl sulphides and 2-carboxyphenyl sulphones can be regarded as potential antitubercular compounds. Since the biological processes of drugs, such as drug absorption, distribution and elimination are functions of acid-base properties of the molecules, we determined the base-dissociation constants (pK_b) of such compounds. The results are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

plotted against E_{HNP} . The slope 19.40 indicates that in glacial acetic acid 19.40 mV is equal to 1 pK_b unit. Base dissociation constant of amino-sulphides, aminosulphones and Schiff bases are computed using the equation based on Kolling and Lambert^{2,3} comparative method,

$$pK_b^* = 6.58 - \frac{(415 - E_{HNP})}{19.40}$$

where, pK_b^* is the base dissociation constant of unknown base in acetic acid, E_{HNP} the half-neutralisation potential (mV) for unknown base at 0.004 M concentration in acetic acid and 6.58 and 415

TABLE 1—BASE DISSOCIATION CONSTANT OF ANTI-TUBERCULAR COMPOUNDS IN ACETIC ACID AT 25° (CB = 0.004 M)

Sl no	R	R'	E_{HNP} (mV)	pK_b^*
1	H	S	432	7.45
2	H	SO ₂	560	14.05
3	Cl	S	446	8.18
4	Cl	SO ₂	578	14.98
5	CH ₃	S	428	7.30
6	CH ₃	SO ₂	555	13.79
7	OCH ₃	S	438	7.76
8	OCH ₃	SO ₂	570	14.57

* pK_b values computed from sodium acetate as reference base

Results and Discussion

Base dissociation constants and half-neutralisation potentials of various bases in CH₃COOH determined by us agree with those by Kolling and Garber¹.

Linear relationship was observed if pK_b^* values were

TABLE 2—BASE DISSOCIATION CONSTANT OF THE COMPOUNDS IN ACETIC ACID AT 25° (CB = 0.004 M)

Sl no	R	R'	E_{HNP} (mV)	pK_b^*
1	H	C ₆ H ₅	435	7.65
2	Cl	C ₆ H ₅	452	8.48
3	H	<i>p</i> -NHCOCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	424	6.99
4	Cl	<i>p</i> -NHCOCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	443	8.02
5	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	452	8.43
6	Cl	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	468	9.31
7	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	426	7.15
8	Cl	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	438	7.76
9	H	<i>p</i> -N-(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	384	4.98
10	Cl	<i>p</i> -N-(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	391	5.31
11	H	5-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₂ O (furan)	498	10.85
12	Cl	5-NO ₂ -C ₄ H ₂ O (furan)	483	10.08

* pK_b values computed from sodium acetate as reference base

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are pK_b and half-neutralisation potential (mV) for sodium acetate (reference base) at 0.004 M concentration in acetic acid as reported by Kolthoff and Bruckenstein³. The base dissociation constants are reported in Tables 1 and 2.

Base dissociation constants in water : The base strengths in water are obtained by simply adding 3.00 (the strengthening factor in acetic acid) to the pK_b value in acetic acid,

$$pK_b(\text{H}_2\text{O}) = pK_b(\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}) + 3.00$$

Percent ionisation of aminosulphides, aminosulphones and Schiff base in water at various pH can be obtained using Handerson-Hasselbalch equation.

Experimental

Acetic acid (ExcellaR) and other chemicals were of G.R., E. Merck or AnalaR grade.

Basic compounds were titrated potentiometrically

using a Systronic 335 pH meter with glass and saturated calomel electrode assembly. pH meter was calibrated using the method described by Kolthoff and Bruckenstein³.

Titration were performed at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in inert atmosphere.

Titration of amines and Schiff bases : Each compound (0.004 mol) dissolved in anhydrous acetic acid (1000 ml) served as the stock solution. The stock solution (50 ml) was transferred into the cell titrated against standard (0.025 M) perchloric acid solution with stirring.

References

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